

Anne Fouilloux

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Summary

Open Science and FAIR Software and Data Advocate.

Focus on strengthening the Nordic position within climate modeling by leveraging, reinforcing and complementing ongoing national, European and world-wide initiatives. Interested in emerging technologies and passionate about bridging skills between different sets of expertise.

Review and evaluate project proposals for the European Commission.

Worked within academia, International organizations and small companies in Norway, United Kingdom & France.

Hold a Master's degree in Computer Science and a PhD's degree focused on Remote Sensing and cloud modelling from the University of Clermont-Ferrand (France).

Ask me about the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), FAIR software, the Galaxy Climate Science Workbench and/or the Nordic Earth System Modelling Hub.

Pronouns: She/her/hers

Experience

Research Engineer

Simula Research Laboratory

Oct 2022 - Present (6 months)

Project Leader

The Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC)

Apr 2020 - Present (3 years)

Lead and manage the second phase of the Nordic Collaboration on e-Infrastructures for Earth System Modelling Tools project (NICEST-2, (2020 – 2023) that focuses on strengthening the Nordic position within climate modelling by leveraging, reinforcing and complementing ongoing initiatives.

My work consists in managing and leading 15 project members to:

- Enhance the performance and optimize and homogenize workflows used, so climate models (like EC-EARTH and NorESM) can be run in an efficient way on future computing resources (like EuroHPC);
- Improve Earth System Model portability by developing and testing containers (docker, singularity, sarus) for running Earth System Models workflows (from laptop to EuroHPC);
- Co-design, develop and deploy operational Climate Tools in the Galaxy climate Workbench for accessible, reproducible, and transparent climate modelling research;
- Widen the usage and expertise on evaluating Earth System Models and develop diagnostics for the Nordics.
- Create a roadmap for FAIRification of Nordic climate model data.

Research Software Engineer

University of Oslo (UiO)

Sep 2013 - Sep 2022 (9 years 1 month)

Lead E-infrastructure and Research Software Engineer Activities of the Department for Geoscience and climate applications running on the Norwegian National Infrastructure (Notur & norStore).

- Digital Technology Lead of the MACHINE learning, Surface mass balance of glaciers, Snow cover, In-situ data, Volume change, Earth observation (MASSIVE) project. Funded by the Norwegian Research Council (2021 – 2025)
- UiO – Geosciences Principal Investigator of the INFRAEOSC-07-2020 project Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC (RELIANCE) (2021-2022).
- UiO- Geosciences Principal Investigator of the H2020 EU project EOSC-Nordic (2019-2022) for the Climate Open Science Demonstrator in Work package 5. Contribute to Open Science take up in the Nordics and lead Climate Galaxy web portal (<https://climate.usegalaxy.eu/>) as part of the delivery of Climate services for cross-disciplinary research such as climate and its economic impact on society.

Senior Consultant

Innova5 Consulting

Jan 2018 - Apr 2020 (2 years 4 months)

Defined the core values of the company and build its strategic vision. Contributed in writing EU proposals.

Senior Analyst

European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

Dec 2005 - Sep 2013 (7 years 10 months)

Responsible of the Observational DataBase (ODB) software, an had-hoc parallel database used at ECMWF, UK Metoffice, Australian Bureau of Meteorology, Meteo-France, HIRLAM (High Resolution Limited Area Model) and ALADIN communities (more than 16 countries).

Responsible of the usage of ODB in the highly parallel Integrated Forecasting System for both operational and research work.

Research Engineer

CNRS

Oct 2001 - Dec 2005 (4 years 3 months)

Assist users to fully take advantage of IDRIS (Institut du Développement et des Ressources en Informatique Scientifique) computing facilities (porting, optimisation and parallelisation of user codes); Participation to EU projects such as DEISA (Distributed European Infrastructure for Supercomputing Applications); Teaching (Fortran, MPI, complexity, theory of languages) both at IDRIS and University.

Researcher

LCPC

Sep 1999 - Oct 2001 (2 years 2 months)

Design of the architecture of the Intelligent Transport System in France; Development of a real time software to control (speed/direction) an automated vehicle prototype.

Postdoctoral position

CERFACS

1998 - 1999 (1 year)

Design and development of PALM (Projet d'Assimilation par Logiciel Multi-Méthodes) software (C/F90, MPI-2). PALM is a generalized coupler which ensures the correct link and synchronization of the software components of the data assimilation suite and which handles the algebra of the problem.

For more information see <http://www.cerfacs.fr/3-26888-The-PALM-Software.php>

Non-tenure staff in the Physics Department

University of Clermont-Ferrand, France

1997 - 1998 (1 year)

Non-tenure staff in the Physics Department

Lectures in mathematics and fluid mechanics (master's level), research on assimilation of satellite data in a regional atmospheric meso-scale model (RAMS).

Education

Ecole normale supérieure

Master's Degree, Computer Science

1990 - 1993

University Clermont-II (Aubière, France)

Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.), Meteorology, cloud modelling, remote sensing and satellite data processing

1994 - 1997

Our first objective was to compare various tools for the assessment of pertinent information (cloud cover, optical thickness and particule size) from AVHRR (Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer) imagery. It led to the development of a new neural method called ACNN (Adjustable Combination of Neural Networks).

The second objective was to improve the initialization procedure of the RAMS (Regional Atmospheric Modelling System) of Pielke and Cotton (1982). We used RAMS in non-hydrostatic mode with full microphysics (Flatau et al., 1989) and radiative transfer (Chen and Cotton, 1983) schemes, with dual nested grids allowing zooms on selected geographical areas. On two case studies, several comparisons made between the model outputs and the corresponding aircraft measurements have shown that the assimilation of the cloud cover derived from satellite observations thanks to our new algorithm supplies an excellent three-dimensional representation of the whole cloud system.

University Clermont-II (Aubière, France)

Diplôme d'Etudes Approfondies (ISCED 6), Meteorology and atmospheric water cycle

1993 - 1994

Skills

Programming • Fortran • Parallel Computing • Technical Support • C++ • Python • Perl •
Meteorology • Numerical Analysis • C